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- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE IMPORTANCE OF STEAM TECHNOLOGY IN DEVELOPING TECHNICAL CREATIVITY AND ENGINEERING SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the relevance of developing technical creativity and engineering skills in preschool children, highlighting its key features. It also explores the positive and beneficial necessity of modern development. The article aims to provide methodological recommendations for fostering technical creativity and engineering skills in preschool children.

Key words: preschool education, child, teacher, parents, methods, game, making, construction, project, activity, innovation, STEAM technology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda texnik ijodkorlik va muhandislik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning dolzarbligi va uning o'ziga xos jihatlari muhokama qilinadi. Shuningdek, zamonaviy rivojlanish uchun bu jarayonning ijobiy va foydali zaruriyati ochib beriladi. Maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda texnik ijodkorlik va muhandislik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha uslubiy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish maqsad qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim, bola, o'qituvchi, ota-onalar, usullar, o'yin, yasash, qurilish, loyiha, faoliyat, innovatsiya, STEAM texnologiyasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается актуальность развития технического творчества и инженерных навыков у детей дошкольного возраста, а также их ключевые особенности. Раскрывается позитивная и полезная необходимость данного процесса для современного развития. В статье предлагаются методические рекомендации по развитию технического творчества и инженерных навыков у детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, ребенок, педагог, родители, методы, игра, изготовление, конструирование, проект, деятельность, инновация, STEAM технология.

INTRODUCTION

The training of future engineers should not begin at universities but much earlier—starting from preschool age—when children's interest in technical creativity becomes evident. It is essential to foster technical thinking, analytical intelligence, and other personal qualities from an early stage. Therefore, preschool educational institutions are tasked with developing children's design and creative abilities. It is crucial to nurture a child who can think creatively, navigate the world of high-tech equipment, and independently create new technical innovations. At the present stage of pedagogical activity, the implementation of innovative programs—including the development of engineering thinking—has become highly relevant and is subject to rigorous requirements.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of cultivating future independent life skills, developing personal competencies in preschool children, and preparing them for engineering from an early age is both urgent and significant. Addressing this challenge involves fostering children's ability to work, practice self-service, participate in household activities,

and engage in creative tasks by introducing them to adult labor. As a result, they will be better prepared for both production processes and real-life conditions.

Modern research suggests that specialized engineering schools, such as Presidential Schools, will continue to evolve in the future. According to scientists, the demand for technical engineers is increasing each year, along with a growing interest in research, scientific exploration, and the integration of science with practical applications. Engineering serves as the driving force behind a society's economic development.

This process involves clarifying, systematizing, and enhancing preschool children's knowledge of social and domestic life, as well as various fields such as production, construction, design, textiles, light industry, technical and technological processes, crafts, and entrepreneurship. Our primary goal is to ensure high-quality school preparation for children in preschool educational institutions.

Engineering thinking is defined as a type of cognitive activity focused on researching, creating, and utilizing new, highly efficient, and reliable equipment, as well as advanced technologies, automation, and mechanization of production to enhance product quality. The essence of engineering thinking lies in solving specific tasks and achieving defined goals through technical means, ultimately yielding the most effective and high-quality results. Additionally, rationalization, inventions, and discoveries—outcomes of scientific and technical creativity—contribute to groundbreaking advancements in science and technology, distinguished by their uniqueness and originality.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In our scientific research, we effectively utilized interactive methods such as SWOT analysis, interviews, and brainstorming to generate and present ideas based on specific examples. The key tasks for fostering the necessary conditions for engineering thinking include developing, discussing, and refining thematic educational programs, scientific and educational laboratory activities, STEM projects, and technical problem-solving initiatives; implementing educational activities within scientific and educational laboratories, STEM projects, and technical problem-solving programs; evaluating the outcomes of these activities; executing the initiatives within the project framework; considering the social applications and involvement of parents (or legal representatives) in the project; preparing reports on project progress; and conducting project implementation reviews by the creative team every two months. This structured approach ensures the systematic development and evaluation of engineering-oriented educational programs and projects.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study aims to explore the relevance and necessity of developing technical creativity and engineering skills in preschool children. It examines the practical benefits of fostering engineering artistry in young learners, particularly during this era of rapid technological advancement. Additionally, the study focuses on nurturing children's ability to predict and innovate in this direction. To enhance children's technical creativity in preschool educational organizations, it is recommended to implement structured activities that involve solving small project-based problems. The following approaches are suggested: Encouraging independent activities in a social and domestic needs center through interactive games such as "We Repair Household Appliances", "I Sew a Dress for My Doll", "We Make Toys", "We Work with Robotics", "A Trip to a Clothing Store". Teaching children to organize their own workspace and cultivate a culture of responsibility in maintaining it. Helping them evaluate their work and that of their peers based on the results, quality, and significance of completed tasks, as well as the time required for completion. Ensuring children understand the purpose of their work by asking questions such as "Why do we need to do this?", "What is the intended goal of this task?". Guiding them to follow a structured plan and complete tasks within a designated timeframe.

A crucial part of this initiative is engaging children in meaningful discussions, encouraging them to reflect on their work process: What are we doing?, What steps do we need to take?, What materials, tools, and equipment are required?, How should we arrange these materials to ensure efficiency?, How should we begin and continue our work?, How do we properly complete the work? Additionally, children participate in various creative and technical projects, including developing models such as "My House" and "Smart City" to promote construction-related activities, exploring the art of sewing and knitting, making clothes for dolls, ironing, and showcasing their creative work, engaging in role-playing activities involving attributes, characters, and storytelling to enhance imagination and technical skills, utilizing game-based learning to facilitate discussions and activities such as "Builder-Builder", "Seller-Seller", "What Tools Do We Need to Work?", "Where Do We Start?".

Properly organizing independent labor activities in preschoolers contributes to high-quality results. Technical creativity, when integrated into projects, enhances children's ability to engage in manual work. Through hands-on experiences, they create new objects, models, and innovations while developing essential skills such

as drawing, painting, cutting, gluing, crafting, sawing, hammering nails, sewing, knitting, and understanding craftsmanship, as well as engineering and problem-solving skills. This process fosters creativity, intelligence, technical competency, and persistence in completing tasks. Furthermore, it nurtures an aesthetic sense, allowing children to take pride in their work and appreciate the value of hard work. Ultimately, these experiences help prepare children for the future, enabling them to explore different professions and develop fundamental skills from an early age.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Preschool children's technical creativity skills encompass drawing, coloring, cutting, gluing, making, sawing, nailing, sewing, knitting, and other basic craft and engineering-related abilities. Through these activities, they gain insight into the secrets of craftsmanship and engineering art. In the process, children develop creativity, technical ingenuity, intelligence, and, most importantly, the ability to complete what they start. Additionally, they cultivate an aesthetic sense, take pleasure in their work and its outcomes, and learn to value hard work. These experiences help prepare them for their future lives, enabling them to freely choose a profession, understand it, and apply their skills in practice from an early age.

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